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In February 2024, the proton accelerator facility HIPA at PSI celebrated its 50th anniversary. Among the revellers was 88-year-old Christa Markovits. She was a pioneer of the Swiss Institute for Nuclear Research and the only woman among the builders of HIPA. She is also a contemporary witness to the history of Europe in the 20th Century.

Christa Markovits was born in Budapest in 1936, just as clouds of World War II gathered ominously. Her early years were marked by the chilling realities of war. And the end of that war meant the start of the iron grip by Soviet occupation, causing further hardship and deprivation. Her journey to pioneering work in nuclear research paints a portrait of resilience against a backdrop of history's darkest moments. "I was fourteen when I decided that I wanted to attend technical high school," she remembers at 88 years old, sitting on a sofa in her study at home in a quiet residential district in Basel. Given the circumstances, it was a pragmatic decision. Had she had the choice, she might have studied history of art. However, her father was an architect who owned a firm, and he was considered a capitalist in communist Hungary. Only proletarians and peasant children were admitted to university studies.

Christa Markovits had figured out how to achieve a decent work in her future. She knew that a matriculation certificate combined with a diploma in machine engineering obtained at a technical high school would provide access to the Technical University of Budapest.

But even though she passed the admission exams year after year, she was only allowed to go to university two years later. In the meantime, Christa had to find something else to do. So, she started working in a former Siemens factory that produced X-ray machines.

The factory supervisor placed Christa Markovits in the office. According to the communist regime's five-year plan, the teenager placed orders for parts of X-ray machines. "That was beautiful work," she recalls. She had to make sure that all the material necessary was available for the production of the X-ray machines that were going to be exported worldwide, as far as China.

In the two years Christa Markovits worked at the factory, she learned all the six-digit serial numbers of all the parts of the machines by heart and knew exactly which part went where. She was intrigued by these machines and became curious to find out how they did what they did.

The Hungarian Revolution of 1956

Finally, the Technical University admitted her to study engineering. Christa Markovits was 20 years old and three weeks into her undergraduate studies when the Hungarian Uprising against the one-party socialist regime gained mo-

mentum. Twelve days later, Soviet tanks entered the country.

Christa Markovits decided to flee from Hungary—along with a quarter million of her compatriots. The young woman chose to set out on her own; her parents and sisters would only head west months later. "I crossed fields and thorny hedges to get to the Austro-Hungarian border," Christa Markovits remembers.

On the road, she joined a young couple with their baby. "When we saw the flares of the Soviet missiles, we had to lie flat on the ground. It was already freezing, and there was snow. I only had a small bag with me, containing my last salary from the factory."

A large part of the salary – and a salami sausage she carried with her – was used to pay a peasant, who led them to the border. Two days later she arrived in Vienna, where she stayed in a makeshift shelter – a primary school gymnasium, the floor lined with mattresses and bags of straw.

Christa Markovits recalls that the city hall in Vienna had been completely restructured for the Hungarian refugees. There were desks with little flags on every floor. On the second floor, there was a desk with a Swiss flag. Even though she had never been there, she knew that she wanted to go to Switzerland. Her father had once told her that Switzerland was the best country in the world because it was peaceful and neutral.

The young woman stood by the Swiss desk in the city hall of Vienna every day from morning until the evening until, one day, a lady told her that she would be given a spot to go to Switzerland. A train organized by the Red Cross took her to the promised land, where she was put in a barrack in Walenstadt. She stayed there for a couple of weeks.

"We were given forms to fill in about what we could do and what we wanted to do," Christa Markovits recalls. "I wrote there that I had finished the technical high school, worked in a factory for X-ray machines, and that wanted to study Physics."

At that time, Fritz Houtermans was an ordinarius professor of physics at the University of Berne. He had offered to take on eager physics students from Hungary. So, Christa Markovits was sent to Berne.

The University officials must have been surprised, that it was a girl that wrote down physics on her form. Much more so than nowadays, women were hugely outnumbered by men in the field of physics. The University of Berne cannot make reliable statements about the proportion of women in physics in 1956, as the data was not yet collected at that time.

The database for Historical Statistics of Switzerland (HSSO) provides the student numbers of the University of Bern by faculty. In the academic year 1956/57, of the 351 students enrolled at the faculty of Philosophy II, which included the subject of physics, a mere 23 were women. This corresponds to a share of 6.5%, and presumably even less for physics.

Christa Markovits was not only one of the very few women at the faculty, she also hardly spoke any German. Luckily, she knew some English. The authorities placed her with a Bernese family with three children. She shared a room with the family's daughter, was given books, and learned German. "The family was very nice and we became friends quickly."

After a year with the family, Christa Markovits received a small scholarship. During her studies, she moved from mansard to mansard. During lunch breaks, she would sell flowers at a stall near the railway station to earn extra income. But still, she could not afford lunch at the canteen with her colleagues.

"I was happy," Christa Markovits hastens to point out. Her studies went well. "Only once did I have a crisis." She was working on her diploma thesis in geological radiometry. The whole process of geological sample preparation was new to her. After she was instructed in the technique, she was left to work on her own in a lab on the second sublevel of the building.

Every now and then, she had to go upstairs to use the precision scale. "People turned away from me when they saw me coming," Christa Markovits recalls. They heard the crackling of the Geiger-Müller-tubes. "I was really lonely". During the writing of her diploma thesis, she suffered from anxiety attacks and sometimes had difficulties leaving her home. She sought treatment for her anxiety and was glad to be able to talk to a group of Hungarian refugees that regularly met in Bern, where she eventually also met her later husband, musicologist Michael Markovits.

In 1964, she successfully completed her thesis titled "Radioactivity Measurements of Lead of Volcanic Origin from the Mount Vesuvius", supervised by Professor F. G. Houtermans at the University of Berne.

From atomic clock to cyclotron to cancer treatment

After finishing her studies, Christa Markovits continued working for the University of Berne. As an assistant, she organized practical workshops for students. She was also regularly sent to the High Altitude Research Station on Jungfrauoch at 3454 meters above sea level, to take care of the apparatus for the automatic measurement of cosmic radiation. She had to change films, valves, do repairs – all on her own. Digitalisation was yet unknown, it was a completely analogue world.

It was strenuous. It would take the young woman four hours to get to the High Altitude Research Station, which often made it impossible to return the same day. But she liked it. "I always liked working, and I always got along well with my colleagues," Christa Markovits says. Nevertheless,

Born Krisztina Barabas in 1936 into a family with Jewish ancestors in Budapest, Hungary, Christa Markovits's early years were tainted by the ominous shadow of Nazi occupation. Forced to wear the yellow star of David and hidden for months in various shelters throughout Budapest, Christa Markovits's survival during the Holocaust was a testament to her family's resourcefulness and a stroke of fortuitous luck.

Of the approximately 800'000 Hungarian Jews, only 200'000 survived the Holocaust. Christa Markovits (she adapted her first name to be easier to spell for the Swiss) wrote an autobiographical testimony about what she and her family lived through in World War II. Together with 14 other survivors of the Holocaust it was published by Suhrkamp, in a collaboration with the Swiss Foreign Department. The anthology is named "Mit meiner Vergangenheit lebe ich" (all texts in German):

<https://www.suhrkamp.de/buch/mit-meiner-vergangenheit-lebe-ich-t-9783633542772>

Following the war's end, Christa Markovits's path led her through the tumultuous landscape of post-war Europe, ultimately finding refuge in Switzerland. In the aftermath of the Hungarian Revolution of 1956, her family was scattered across continents in search of safety. Amidst the chaos of fleeing their homeland, only one of Christa Markovits's sisters was granted entry into Switzerland, defying the authorities' decree to close their doors to further refugees.

Despite all the challenges, Christa Markovits determinedly pursued her studies. Her journey from a factory worker in Budapest to a pioneering physicist in Switzerland exemplifies an indomitable spirit. Yet, it is crucial to also acknowledge the additional layers of adversity she likely faced as a woman in a predominantly male-dominated field. Physics, like many STEM disciplines, has historically been a challenging terrain for women to navigate. From ingrained biases to systemic barriers, the path for female physicists has often been layered with obstacles. For Christa Markovits, studying physics as a refugee, separated from her family, and in a foreign language would have undoubtedly magnified these challenges.

Institutional biases and gender stereotypes may have hindered her recognition and advancement, despite her undeniable talents and contributions. The narrative of her journey serves as a poignant reminder of the resilience required of women who dare to carve out careers in fields where they are underrepresented.

Christa Markovits's story prompts reflection on the importance of addressing gender disparities and fostering inclusivity within academic and scientific communities, ensuring that all individuals, regardless of gender, have equal opportunities to thrive and be recognized for their achievements.

Today she lives as a widow alone and is busy with the publication of the manuscripts of her late husband she loved. Without grandparents, they could not afford to establish a family with children.

she began looking for a job outside her university. "I never dreamed of making a discovery of my own," she says. "But I know my strengths. My vision was working in a team on interesting projects with fellow physicists, engineers and technicians." Finally this dream came true at SIN and PSI a couple of years later.

Before that, an opportunity opened up at the Neuchatel Observatory, where she was involved in research on a new type of atomic clock, replacing caesium by thallium. After three years at the Neuchatel Observatory, Christa Markovits followed Professor Jean Pierre Blaser, the former director of the observatory, to ETH Zurich.

She assisted him in his lectures and co-edited his textbooks. Blaser was involved in promoting nuclear energy in Switzerland and planned to build a proton cyclotron complementary to the machines at CERN.

In response to his efforts, the Swiss parliament founded the Swiss Institute for Nuclear Research (SIN) in 1968. The proton accelerator was the core of the SIN. Protons were accelerated to approximately 80 percent of the speed of light before being directed onto targets. The collisions in carbon targets produced pions and muons, and the collisions with lead targets produced neutrons.

Christa Markovits was in charge of designing and building the beamline leading the protons from the 72 MeV injector cyclotron to the 590 MeV main accelerator, today called HIPA. She was the only female scientist on the team. A picture of the inauguration of the cyclotron in 1974 shows her in the middle of the circularly aligned magnets, wearing a bright red sweater. She later worked as head of the control room at the proton accelerator, often at night and on weekends.

In 1988, SIN merged with the Federal Institute for Reactor Research (EIR) right across the Aare River, and the newly founded research facility was named the Paul Scherrer Institute (PSI). The 1990s marked the emergence of cancer treatment with protons at PSI, an activity which had been developed at SIN: A new and exciting field of research for Christa Markovits.

Christa Markovits during the HIPA celebration in February 2024 in front of the inauguration picture from 1974, which is still exhibited at PSI. Photo: David George

She was involved in the eye irradiation project (OPTIS) for many years until her retirement in 1996. "I was responsible for the physical part of the project, the guidance of the proton beam and the safety", she says. It was a pioneer project – OPTIS was the first facility of its kind in Europe, and patients came from all over the world.

At the beginning, the proton beam traveled 40 meters before it reached the patient's eye with an accuracy of microns. Nowadays, the accelerator has a fixed beamline, and the patient is moved in front of it. "I was and still am enthusiastic about the OPTIS project", Christa Markovits says.

This was confirmed by her group leader in the Accelerator Division of PSI at the time: "Her experience in beam optics, the perfect preparation of shutdown work and the detailed and precise documentation of the systems entrusted to her have enabled successful accelerator operation", he wrote in a reference letter for her retirement.

He continues: "If both the control room and the medical staff can enjoy problem-free OPTIS operation today, it is not least thanks to the dedicated commitment and coordination of Ms. Markovits." And ends with: "She was a very pleasant employee who maintained a good relationship with her colleagues and superiors thanks to her balanced and friendly manner."

Never someone to boast about her own achievements, Christa Markovits was very happy about that reference letter. Even though it was only at the very end of her career, she felt acknowledged for her work at last. When she received the invitation to celebrate the 50th anniversary of HIPA, she was delighted. And she enjoyed every minute she got to spend with her old colleagues.